

KINDERGARTEN TEACHERS' EFFICACY, WORK ENGAGEMENT, JOB SATISFACTION AND SUPERVISORY NEEDS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of respondents' profile, efficacy, job satisfaction, and supervisory needs on work engagement among kindergarten teachers in the Division of Bohol for the school year 2025–2026. Specifically, it described the respondents' profile in terms of years of teaching experience, undergraduate program, highest educational attainment, and trainings attended, and determined their levels of efficacy, work engagement, job satisfaction, and supervisory needs. A predictive research design was employed using a survey questionnaire administered to 286 kindergarten teachers from selected sub-congressional districts. Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and multiple linear regression. Findings revealed that teachers demonstrated a high level of efficacy, were highly engaged in their work, and were very satisfied with their jobs. However, they exhibited a high level of supervisory needs. Efficacy and job satisfaction were found to be significant positive predictors of work engagement. In contrast, supervisory needs, years of teaching experience, training, and undergraduate program were not significant predictors. Among the categories of highest educational attainment, having a Diploma in Early Childhood Education was associated with higher work engagement, while being at the CAR doctoral level was associated with lower engagement. The study concluded that work engagement among kindergarten teachers is primarily influenced by efficacy and job satisfaction, along with specific educational qualifications. It is recommended that school leaders implement district-based training programs focused on strengthening supervisory support in curriculum planning and inclusive classroom practices. Future studies may explore additional variables and incorporate qualitative approaches to further understand teachers' work engagement.

Keywords: *teacher efficacy, work engagement, job satisfaction, supervisory needs, kindergarten teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Kindergarten education plays a vital role in shaping the early learning experiences of children. At this stage, teachers do not only introduce basic literacy and numeracy skills but also help young learners develop social, emotional, and behavioral foundations needed for later schooling. Because kindergarten serves as the entry point to formal education, the work of kindergarten teachers requires patience, confidence, creativity, and strong instructional competence.

In recent years, the responsibilities of kindergarten teachers have become more demanding. Learners enter school with different home backgrounds, levels of readiness, behaviors, and learning needs. Some children still need support in listening, following instructions, managing emotions, and interacting with others. These realities make kindergarten teaching more complex, especially as teachers are expected to provide inclusive, developmentally appropriate, and engaging learning experiences.

Teacher efficacy is an important factor in meeting these demands. Teachers who believe in their ability to teach effectively are more likely to use appropriate instructional strategies, manage the classroom well, and engage learners meaningfully. In the kindergarten setting, efficacy is especially important because teachers deal with young children who require close guidance, constant motivation, and differentiated support. Studies have shown that teachers with strong self-efficacy tend to be more resilient, adaptable, and confident in addressing classroom challenges (Hussain et al., 2022; Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2021).

Work engagement is another important concern in the teaching profession. Engaged teachers show energy, dedication, and focus in their work. For kindergarten teachers, engagement is reflected in their willingness to prepare meaningful activities, respond to learners' needs, and remain committed despite workload pressures. However, work engagement may be affected by several factors, including teachers' efficacy, job satisfaction, supervisory support, workload, and working conditions.

Job satisfaction also plays a significant role in teachers' motivation and performance. When teachers feel supported, valued, and given opportunities for professional growth, they are more likely to remain committed to their work. On the other hand, heavy workload, limited resources, low morale support, and dissatisfaction with salary and benefits may weaken their enthusiasm and engagement. For kindergarten teachers, job satisfaction is important because their work requires emotional labor, patience, and consistent interaction with young learners.

Supervisory needs are likewise essential in improving teaching quality. Kindergarten teachers need guidance in content knowledge and pedagogy, learning

environment, diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, and assessment and reporting. Appropriate supervision helps teachers improve their instructional practices, address classroom concerns, and respond to learners' developmental needs. Supervision should not only focus on compliance but should also serve as a supportive process that helps teachers grow professionally.

This study is anchored on key theories that explain the relationship among teacher efficacy, work engagement, job satisfaction, and supervisory needs. The Job Demands–Resources Theory explains how work engagement is influenced by job demands and available resources or support (Bakker et al., 2023). Meanwhile, Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory highlights how factors such as working conditions, salary, recognition, professional growth, and support influence job satisfaction (as cited in Alshmemri et al., 2017). Furthermore, Glickman's Developmental Supervision Theory explains that teachers require different forms of supervision depending on their level of experience, competence, and professional needs (Glickman, 1992).

Although many studies have examined teachers' efficacy, satisfaction, engagement, and supervision, kindergarten teachers remain less explored, particularly in the public-school setting. This gap is important because kindergarten teachers carry a foundational responsibility in the education system. Understanding their efficacy, work engagement, job satisfaction, and supervisory needs can provide useful insights for school heads, supervisors, and education leaders in designing appropriate support programs.

Thus, this study examined the influence of teachers' profile, efficacy, job satisfaction, and supervisory needs on the work engagement of kindergarten teachers in the Division of Bohol during the School Year 2025–2026. The findings served as basis for proposing an action plan that strengthens instructional supervision, supports teacher development, and enhances the professional engagement of kindergarten teachers.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the influence of respondent's profile, efficacy, job satisfaction and supervisory needs on work engagement among the kindergarten teachers in the Division of Bohol during the school year 2025-2026.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 no. of years in teaching experience;
 - 1.2 undergraduate program obtained;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.4 trainings attended?
2. What is the level of efficacy of the respondents in terms:
 - 2.1 instructional strategies;
 - 2.1 classroom management; and
 - 2.1 student engagement?

3. What is the level of work engagement of the respondents in terms:
 - 3.1 vigor;
 - 3.2 dedication; and
 - 3.3 absorption?
4. What is the level of job satisfaction of the respondents in terms:
 - 4.1 working condition;
 - 4.3 professional growth;
 - 4.4 morale support from the school head; and
 - 4.5 salary and benefit?
5. What is the level of teachers' supervisory needs in the PPST domains:
 - 3.1 content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 3.2 learning environment;
 - 3.3 diversity of learners;
 - 3.4 curriculum and planning; and
 - 3.5 assessment and reporting?
6. Do the following significantly predict teachers' level of work engagement:
 - 6.1 respondents profile;
 - 6.2 level of efficacy;
 - 6.3 level of job satisfaction; and
 - 6.4 level of supervisory needs?
7. What action plan can be proposed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a predictive research design to determine the influence of teachers' profile, efficacy, job satisfaction, and supervisory needs on work engagement. This design allowed the researcher to examine which variables significantly predicted the work engagement of kindergarten teachers. Data were gathered using a survey questionnaire.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the Division of Bohol, which served as the research locale. The division is one of the twelve school divisions in Region VII, Central Visayas, and is recognized as one of the largest divisions in the region. It is composed of three congressional districts covering 47 municipalities. The selected schools included in the study were drawn from across the three congressional districts to ensure representation of the division. These schools vary in classification, ranging from small to mega school categories, thereby providing a diverse educational setting. The selection of participating schools was done through cluster sampling, wherein sub-congressional districts were randomly chosen, and schools within these areas were included as part of the study.

Research Participants

The respondents of this study were kindergarten teachers selected to meet the objectives of the research. They were chosen using a cluster sampling technique, wherein sub-congressional districts were randomly identified, and teachers from the selected schools within these clusters were included in the study. This approach ensured that the respondents represented a range of teaching contexts and experiences.

Distributions of Respondents

Congressional District	Total No. of Sub-Congressional District	No. of Selected Sub-Congressional District	No. of Teachers
1	3	2	102
2	4	2	63
3	4	3	121
Total	11	7	286

Research Instrument

This study utilized a modified survey questionnaire as the primary data-gathering tool. The instrument was adapted from established measures and revised to suit the context of kindergarten teachers. It underwent content validation by experts in educational management and psychology, and a pilot test confirmed its reliability, yielding Cronbach's alpha values of 0.77 for efficacy, 0.86 for work engagement, and 0.93 for job satisfaction.

The questionnaire consisted of five parts: (1) respondents' profile; (2) teachers' efficacy, adapted from the Teacher Sense of Efficacy Scale (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001); (3) work engagement, based on the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2003); (4) job satisfaction, adapted and modified from Baggay et al. (2021); and (5) supervisory needs, aligned with the PPST-RPMS instructional supervisory tool.

Research Procedure

Permission to conduct the study was secured from the Dean of the College of Advanced Studies, the Campus Director, and the BISU University President. Approval was also obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent of Bohol, District Supervisors, and School Heads, with endorsement from the dissertation adviser.

The questionnaire was administered to the respondents during the second week of January. Prior to data collection, respondents were informed of the purpose of the study and assured that all information would be treated with strict confidentiality. After the allotted time, the questionnaires were retrieved. The collected data were then tabulated, analyzed, interpreted, and reported.

Data Analysis

The data were subjected to the following statistical treatment to facilitate presentation, analysis and interpretation. To determine the percentage of the profile in terms of years of teaching experience and undergraduate degree program obtained, highest educational attainment, and trainings attended of the kindergarten teachers, the percentage formula was used. To measure the perceived level of efficacy, work engagement, job satisfaction, and supervisory needs, the weighted mean was used. In interpreting the scores of the perceived level of the teachers' efficacy in instructional strategies, classroom management, and student engagement, the 4-point rating scale was used.

Level of Kindergarten Teachers' Efficacy

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Always	Teachers have high level of efficacy.
3	2.50-3.49	Sometimes	Teachers have moderate level of efficacy.
2	1.50-2.49	Seldom	Teachers have slight level of efficacy.
1	1.00-1.49	Never	Teachers have very low level of efficacy.

In interpreting the scores of the teachers' work engagement in vigor, dedication, and absorption, the 4-point rating scale was used.

Level of Kindergarten Teachers' Work Engagement

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Always	Teachers are highly engaged.
3	2.50-3.49	Sometimes	Teachers are moderately engaged.
2	1.50-2.49	Seldom	Teachers are slightly engaged.
1	1.00-1.49	Never	Teachers are disengaged.

In interpreting the scores of teachers' job satisfaction in terms of working conditions, professional growth and morale support from the school heads, the 4-point rating scale was used.

Level of Kindergarten Teachers' Job Satisfaction

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Very Satisfied (VS)	Teachers are highly contented with their job.
3	2.50-3.49	Satisfied (S)	Teachers are contented with their job.
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Satisfied (SS)	Teachers are slightly contented with their job.
1	1.00-1.49	Not Satisfied (NS)	Teachers are discontented with their job.

In interpreting the scores of teachers' supervisory needs in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, and assessment and reporting, the 4-point rating scale was used.

Level of Kindergarten Teachers' Supervisory Needs

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50-4.00	Very High Need	Teacher requires very high instructional supervision.
3	2.50-3.49	High Need	Teacher requires high instructional supervision.

2	1.50-2.49	Moderate Need	Teacher shows moderate need in Instructional Supervision.
1	1.00-1.49	Low Need	Teacher shows low need in instructional supervision.

To determine whether the respondents' profile, level of efficacy, level of job satisfaction, and supervisory needs significantly predict the teachers' level of work engagement, a multiple linear regression analysis was conducted.

RESULTS

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered from the kindergarten teachers in the Division of Bohol. The results are organized according to the specific problems of the study and are presented in both tabular and textual forms. The data on teachers' efficacy, job satisfaction, supervisory needs, and work engagement are analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The findings are interpreted to explain the relationships among variables and to provide insights relevant to the objectives of the study.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents
N= 286

1.1 Years of Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
0-3 years	41	14.3%	3
4-10 years	90	31.5%	2
11-20 years	154	53.8%	1
more than 20 years	1	0.3%	4
1.2 Undergraduate Program	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Bachelor in Elementary Education - General Education with units in Early Childhood Education/PET	214	74.83	1
Bachelor of Early Childhood Education	7	2.45	4
Bachelor in Elementary Education with specialization in Preschool or ECE	29	10.10	2
Bachelor in Elementary Education major in Special Education with 18 units in ECE	23	8.04	3
Bachelor of Elementary Education major in Science/English/Mathematics/Computer Education with 18 units in ECE or Pre-Elementary Teaching	7	2.45	4
Bachelor of Secondary Education with 18 units in Early Childhood Education	6	2.10	5
1.3 Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Bachelor's Degree	77	26.90	2
With Master's Units	118	41.30	1
CAR in Masteral	20	7.00	4
Diploma in Early Childhood Education)	3	1.00	6
Master's Degree	58	20.30	3
With Doctoral Units	2	0.70	7
CAR in Doctoral	3	1.00	6
Doctoral Degree	4	1.40	5
1.4 Training Attended	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Training of School Administrators and Teachers on Kindergarten	212	74.13%	3
Training on the Matatag Curriculum for Teachers	256	89.51%	2

Massive Open Online Course (MOOC): Early Literacy Instruction for K to 3 Teachers	52	18.18%	9
Strengthening Kindergarten Teaching and Learning	163	56.99%	4
Enhancement Training on the National Kindergarten Curriculum	146	51.05%	5
Workshop on the Contextualization of Activities in the 2017 Kin	113	39.51%	7
Understanding Kindergarten Teaching and Learning	118	41.26%	6
Mid-Year Assessment and In-Service Training of Teachers	285	96.65%	1
ICT Literacy Training	48	16.78%	10
Psychological Well-being Promoting Mental Health Awareness in the Midst of New Academic Set-Up	73	25.52%	8

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of years of teaching experience, undergraduate program, highest educational attainment, and trainings attended. In terms of teaching experience, the majority of the respondents (53.8%) have 11–20 years of experience, followed by those with 4–10 years (31.5%), while only a minimal proportion (0.3%) have more than 20 years of experience. This indicates that most respondents are moderately to highly experienced teachers, suggesting that the findings largely reflect the perspectives of experienced practitioners.

With regard to undergraduate program, most respondents (74.83%) are Bachelor of Elementary Education–General Education graduates with units in Early Childhood Education, followed by those with a specialization in Preschool Education (10.10%). Only a small percentage are graduates of Bachelor of Secondary Education with units in Early Childhood Education (2.10%). These results imply that respondents generally meet the minimum qualifications required for kindergarten teaching, although only a few possess specialized degrees in Early Childhood Education.

In terms of highest educational attainment, the largest group (41.30%) has master’s degree units, followed by those holding a bachelor’s degree (26.90%), while only a small proportion have completed doctoral degrees (1.40%). This suggests that many teachers are engaged in continuing education, although completion of advanced degrees remains limited.

Regarding trainings attended, most respondents participated in Mid-Year Assessment and In-Service Training (96.65%) and Matatag Curriculum training (89.51%), along with other curriculum-related and kindergarten-focused programs. However, participation in technology-related trainings such as ICT Literacy (16.78%) and online courses (18.18%) was relatively low, indicating limited engagement in digital and self-directed learning opportunities.

Overall, the profile indicates that respondents are predominantly experienced teachers who actively participate in professional development, although there is a need to strengthen involvement in technology-related training. These findings support the view that teaching experience contributes to professional performance (Mufidah et al., 2021), although it may not always directly determine effectiveness (Pranoto et al., 2021).

Table 2
Efficacy of Kindergarten Teachers
N=286

A. INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES	WM	INT
I. As a kindergarten teacher, I...		
1. can adjust my teaching strategies to help pupils with different learning needs;	3.87	HE
2. provide alternative explanations or play-based activities when children have difficulty understanding a concept	3.86	HE
3. use appropriate teaching materials to support struggling pupils in literacy and numeracy;	3.86	HE
4. can use a variety of assessment strategies to pupils.	3.84	HE
Composite Mean	3.86	HE
B. CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT		
As a kindergarten teacher, I...		
5. can effectively establish a classroom management system with each group of learners;	3.73	HE
6. can guide my pupils to behave appropriately and follow classroom rules;	3.70	HE
7. can handle misbehavior effectively while maintaining a positive and respectful classroom environment; and	3.69	HE
8. can keep my pupils focused, even when they are inattentive, or distracting others during class.	3.62	HE
Composite Mean	3.69	HE
C. LEARNER ENGAGEMENT		
As a kindergarten teacher, I...		
9. can motivate learners who show low interest in school or during classroom activities;	3.85	HE
10. can get my pupils believe they can do well in schoolwork;	3.84	HE
11. can assist learners from disadvantaged backgrounds to do well in school or class.	3.78	HE
Composite Mean	3.82	HE
Grand Mean	3.79	HE

Legend: HE- High Efficacy ME- Moderate Efficacy

Table 2 presents the level of efficacy of kindergarten teachers in terms of instructional strategies, classroom management, and learner engagement. The results reveal a grand mean of 3.79, interpreted as high efficacy, indicating that respondents possess a strong level of confidence in performing their teaching responsibilities.

Among the three domains, instructional strategies obtained the highest composite mean (3.86), suggesting that teachers are highly capable of adapting teaching approaches, utilizing varied assessment strategies, and addressing diverse learner needs. This is followed by learner engagement (3.82), indicating effectiveness in motivating learners, fostering confidence, and supporting pupils from varied backgrounds.

Classroom management recorded the lowest composite mean (3.69), although still within the high efficacy range. This implies that while teachers are generally effective in maintaining classroom order and managing behavior, this domain is comparatively less strong. Overall, the findings indicate that kindergarten teachers demonstrate consistently

high efficacy across all domains, supporting effective instructional practices and positive learner development. These results affirm that teacher efficacy is a key factor influencing teaching performance and learner outcomes (Wisudawati, 2023; Shu, 2022).

Table 3
Work Engagement of Kindergarten Teachers
N=286

A. VIGOR	WM	INT
As a kindergarten teacher, I or I am...		
1. continue working even in times of challenges and difficulties;	3.84	HE
2. feel more energized and motivated in my work;	3.77	HE
3. more excited and energetic while performing my job;	3.74	HE
4. very mentally and emotionally strong at work; and	3.69	HE
5. feel like bursting with energy in my work.	3.48	ME
Composite Mean	3.70	HE
B. DEDICATION		
As a kindergarten teacher, I or I am...		
6. perform my job with full meaning and purpose;	3.90	HE
7. proud of the work that I do;	3.87	HE
8. consistently plan engaging lessons to meet the learning needs of my learners;	3.86	HE
9. like my job and enjoy doing it; and	3.84	HE
10. inspired and find my job meaningful.	3.82	HE
Composite Mean	3.86	HE
C. ABSORPTION		
As a kindergarten teacher, I or I am...		
11. stay mentally connected to my work even after working hours;	3.75	HE
12. deeply involved in challenging tasks yet still find joy in it;	3.72	HE
13. fully focused when teaching pupils that time seems to pass quickly;	3.70	HE
14. remain deeply concentrated in my tasks even on busy times; and	3.66	HE
15. give full attention to my learners while teaching that I hardly notice distractions.	3.65	HE
Composite Mean	3.70	HE
Grand Mean	3.75	HE

Legend: HE- Highly Engaged ME- Moderately Engaged

Table 3 presents the level of work engagement among kindergarten teachers in terms of vigor, dedication, and absorption. The results show a grand mean of 3.75, interpreted as highly engaged, indicating that respondents generally demonstrate a strong level of engagement in their teaching profession. Among the three dimensions, dedication obtained the highest composite mean (3.86), suggesting that teachers perceive their work as meaningful, take pride in their profession, and exhibit strong commitment to their roles.

Vigor and absorption both recorded composite means of 3.70, also interpreted as highly engaged. In terms of vigor, teachers showed energy and persistence in performing their tasks, particularly in continuing work despite challenges. However, one indicator (“feel like bursting with energy in my work”) was rated at a moderate level (WM = 3.48), indicating that some teachers may experience limitations in sustaining high energy levels consistently. For absorption, the findings indicate that teachers are generally focused and

immersed in their work. They remain attentive and engaged during teaching activities, although slightly lower ratings suggest that heavy workload and classroom demands may occasionally affect their level of concentration.

These findings are consistent with Schaufeli et al. (2020), who described work engagement as a positive state characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. Similarly, Bakker and Demerouti (2024) emphasized that highly engaged employees demonstrate greater enthusiasm, commitment, and persistence in their work. Albrecht et al. (2021) further noted that employees are more engaged when they find meaning and purpose in their tasks. In the educational context, teacher engagement has been associated with improved teaching performance and positive classroom outcomes (Maquidato & Bayani, 2024). Overall, the results indicate that kindergarten teachers exhibit a high level of work engagement, with dedication emerging as the strongest dimension, reflecting their strong sense of purpose and commitment to their profession.

Table 4
Job Satisfaction of Kindergarten Teachers
N=286

A. WORKING CONDITION	WM	INT
As a teacher, I am satisfied with...		
1. the atmosphere of trust and respect in the workplace.	3.60	VS
2. the use of the facilities of the school for the activities related to teaching.	3.53	VS
3. the classrooms that are well-ventilated and have good lighting.	3.53	VS
4. the use of possible resources that are available in the school.	3.50	VS
5. the provision of sufficient copies of books, manuals and guidelines.	3.40	S
Composite Mean	3.51	VS
B. PROFESSIONAL GROWTH		
C. As a teacher, I am satisfied with...		
6. The seminar/workshops provided by organization that enhance my strategies in teaching numeracy and literacy.	3.71	VS
7. the opportunities given by administrator to attend seminar/workshops.	3.68	VS
8. the provision of mentoring to ensure good performance.	3.64	VS
9. the opportunities for professional growth in my workplace.	3.64	VS
10. the support from school administrator on my graduate studies.	3.45	S
Composite Mean	3.63	VS
D. MORAL SUPPORT FROM THE SCHOOL HEAD		
As a teacher, I am satisfied with how my school head...		
11. creates an environment that builds friendship, a climate of mutual trust and respect.	3.63	VS
12. shows concern of the well-being and challenges I face in teaching.	3.62	VS
13. provides supportive feedback that helps teachers grow.	3.62	VS
14. motivates at work with enthusiasm.	3.61	VS
15. recognizes the effort I put into work.	3.58	VS
Composite Mean	3.61	VS
E. SALARY AND BENEFIT		
As a teacher, I am satisfied with		
16. the benefits I receive and the range of benefits provided.	3.31	S
17. the organization values and appreciates my work through my salary and benefits.	3.30	S
18. the regularity and timeliness of the salary and salary adjustments.	3.29	S

19. the salary and benefits which are fair within the organization.	3.28	S
20. the salary I am paid for the work I do.	3.26	S
Composite Mean	3.29	S
Grand Mean	3.51	VS

Legend: VS- Very Satisfied S- Satisfied

Table 4 presents the level of job satisfaction of kindergarten teachers across four domains: working conditions, professional growth, moral support from the school head, and salary and benefits. The results reveal a grand mean of 3.51, interpreted as very satisfied, indicating that teachers generally experience a positive level of job satisfaction. Among the domains, professional growth obtained the highest composite mean (3.63), suggesting strong satisfaction with opportunities for seminars, workshops, mentoring, and career advancement.

This is followed by moral support from the school head (3.61), also interpreted as very satisfied, indicating that teachers feel supported, recognized, and motivated by their administrators. Working conditions likewise received a very satisfied rating (3.51), reflecting favorable perceptions of the school environment and available resources, although the provision of instructional materials was rated slightly lower.

In contrast, salary and benefits obtained the lowest composite mean (3.29), interpreted as satisfied. This indicates that financial compensation and benefits are comparatively less satisfactory, with concerns related to adequacy and alignment with workload. Overall, the findings indicate that kindergarten teachers demonstrate a high level of job satisfaction, primarily driven by professional development opportunities and administrative support, while highlighting compensation as an area for improvement. These results affirm that both workplace resources and compensation are key factors influencing job satisfaction (Oyekunle, 2024; Setyaningsih & Sunaryo, 2021).

Table 5
Supervisory Needs of Kindergarten Teachers
N=286

A. CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AND PEDAGOGY	Mean	INT
1. Apply a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	2.99	HN
2. Use a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.	2.97	HN
3. Use effective verbal and non-verbal classroom communication strategies to support learner understanding, participation, engagement and achievement.]	2.97	HN
4. Apply knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	2.94	HN
5. Display proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to facilitate teaching.	2.92	HN
Composite Mean	2.96	HN
B. LEARNING ENVIRONMENT		
6. Manage classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environment.	3.02	HN

7. Apply a range of successful strategies that maintain learning environments that motivate learners to work productively by assuming responsibility for their own learning.	3.01	HN
8. Maintain supportive learning environments that nurture and inspire learners to participate, cooperate and collaborate in continued learning.	3.00	HN
9. Maintain learning environment that promote fairness, respect and care to encourage learning.	2.97	HN
Composite Mean	3.00	HN
C. DIVERSITY OF LEARNERS		
10. Use differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experience.	3.02	HN
11. Establish a learner-centered culture by using teaching strategies that respond to their linguistic, cultural, socio-economic and religious backgrounds.	3.02	HN
12. Design, adapt and implement teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness and talents.	3.00	HN
Composite Mean	3.02	HN
D.CURRICULUM PLANNING		
13. Plan, manage and implement developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	3.01	HN
F. ASSESSMENT AND REPORTING		
14. Design, select, organize and use diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	2.95	HN
Grand Mean	2.99	HN

Legend: HN- High Need

Table 5 presents the supervisory needs of kindergarten teachers across five domains: content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum planning, and assessment and reporting.

The results yielded a grand mean of 2.99, interpreted as high need, indicating that teachers generally require substantial supervisory support across instructional domains. Among the areas, diversity of learners registered the highest composite mean (3.02), followed by curriculum planning (3.01) and learning environment (3.00), all interpreted as high need. These findings suggest that teachers require greater guidance in addressing learner diversity, implementing differentiated instruction, and managing inclusive classroom environments.

In contrast, content knowledge and pedagogy (2.96) and assessment and reporting (2.95) obtained slightly lower means, though still within the high-need category. This indicates that while teachers demonstrate competence in these areas, continued supervision is necessary to further strengthen instructional delivery and assessment practices.

Overall, the consistently high ratings across all domains indicate that supervisory support remains essential in enhancing teaching effectiveness, curriculum implementation, and learner-centered practices. These findings affirm that structured and differentiated supervision is necessary to address teachers' evolving instructional needs (Crowhurst & Cornish, 2020; Gallego & Caingcoy, 2020).

Table 6
Multiple Regression Analysis Predicting Work Engagement

Predictor	Estimate	Stand ard Error	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Interpretati on	Decision (<i>H</i> ₀)
Intercept	0.233	0.141	1.647	.101	<i>Insignificant</i>	<i>Accepted</i>
Efficacy	0.786	0.040	19.879	<.001	Significa nt	Rejected
Job Satisfaction	0.169	0.027	6.194	<.001		
Supervisory Needs Training	-0.017 -0.005	0.012 0.005	-1.456 -1.025	.147 .306	<i>Insignificant</i>	<i>Accepted</i>
Years of Teaching Experience						
4-10 years	-0.032	0.034	-0.944	.346	<i>Insignificant</i>	<i>Accepted</i>
11-20 years	0.013	0.035	0.381	.704		
More than 20 years	0.326	0.173	1.879	.061		
Minimum Educational Attainment						
BEEd-General with ECE units	-0.003	0.037	-0.074	0.941	<i>Insignificant</i>	<i>Accepted</i>
BEED-SPED with 18 units	0.016	0.048	0.334	0.739		
BSED with 18 units BEED	0.075	0.078	0.964	0.336		
Science/Math/English/ Comp	0.055	0.074	0.738	0.461		
Bachelor of ECE	0.058	0.071	0.807	0.420		
Highest Educational Attainment						
With Master's units	0.044	0.028	1.618	0.107	<i>Insignificant</i>	<i>Accepted</i>
Master's Degree	-0.011	0.030	-0.364	0.716		
CAR in Masteral	0.054	0.044	1.223	.222		
Diploma in Early Childhood Education	0.205	0.100	2.048	.042	Significant	Rejected
CAR in Doctoral	-0.324	0.101	-3.205	.002		
With doctoral units	0.010	0.101	0.103	.918	<i>Insignificant</i>	<i>Accepted</i>
Doctoral degree	-0.083	0.088	-0.946	.345		

Model Summary: $R = .866, R^2 = .750, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .732, F(19,266) = 42, p < .001$

Note: Reference categories – 0-3 years teaching experience; BEED-in Preschool or ECE for minimum educational attainment; Bachelor's degree for highest educational attainment

Table 6 presents the results of the multiple regression analysis examining the predictors of work engagement among kindergarten teachers. The overall model was statistically significant, $F(19, 266) = 42, p < .001$, explaining 75% of the variance in work engagement ($R^2 = .750$). This indicates that the set of predictors collectively provides a strong explanation of teachers' engagement levels.

Among the variables, efficacy ($B = 0.786, p < .001$) and job satisfaction ($B = 0.169, p < .001$) emerged as significant positive predictors of work engagement. This suggests that teachers who demonstrate higher confidence in their teaching abilities and greater satisfaction with their profession are more likely to exhibit stronger engagement in their

work. These findings support Heng and Chu (2023) and Han and Wang (2021), who emphasized that teacher self-efficacy is a key determinant of work engagement. Similarly, Wang et al. (2020) and Zang and Feng (2023) highlighted the strong link between job satisfaction and professional commitment.

In contrast, supervisory needs, training, years of teaching experience, and undergraduate program were not significant predictors, indicating that these variables do not directly influence work engagement when psychological factors are considered. This finding aligns with the Job Demands–Resources model, which posits that personal resources, such as self-efficacy, exert a stronger influence on engagement than structural or external factors. With respect to highest educational attainment, most categories were not significant. However, having a Diploma in Early Childhood Education ($B = 0.205$, $p = .042$) was associated with higher work engagement, while being at the CAR doctoral level ($B = -0.324$, $p = .002$) was associated with lower engagement compared to those with a bachelor's degree. These variations suggest that specific professional pathways may influence engagement differently. Overall, the findings indicate that internal psychological factors particularly efficacy and job satisfaction are the strongest predictors of work engagement, while demographic and structural variables show limited direct influence.

DISCUSSION

This study examined the levels of efficacy, work engagement, job satisfaction, and supervisory needs among kindergarten teachers in the Division of Bohol for the school year 2025–2026. It also determined whether these variables and selected profile characteristics predict work engagement. A predictive research design was used, with data collected through a validated and pilot-tested survey questionnaire. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, weighted mean) and multiple regression analysis were employed. The findings provided a basis for understanding the factors influencing teachers' work engagement.

Findings

Based on the data gathered, the following findings were established:

- 1. Profile of the Kindergarten Teachers.** Most respondents had 11–20 years of teaching experience and held a Bachelor in Elementary Education – General Education with units in Early Childhood Education as their minimum qualification. In terms of highest educational attainment, the majority had master's degree units. Most teachers attended Mid-Year In-Service Training (INSET) and training on the MATATAG Curriculum, while participation in ICT-related and online courses was relatively low.
- 2. Teachers' Level of Efficacy.** Kindergarten teachers demonstrated a high level of efficacy, with a grand mean of 3.79. Instructional strategies obtained the highest mean (3.86), followed by learner engagement (3.82), while classroom management had the lowest mean (3.69), though still within the high level.

3. **Teachers' Level of Work Engagement.** Teachers were highly engaged, with a grand mean of 3.75. Dedication recorded the highest mean (3.86), followed by vigor and absorption, both with means of 3.70.
4. **Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction.** Teachers were generally very satisfied, with a grand mean of 3.51. Professional growth ranked highest (3.63), followed by moral support from the school head (3.61) and working conditions (3.51). Salary and benefits obtained the lowest mean (3.29), though still interpreted as satisfied.
5. **Teachers' Level of Supervisory Needs.** Teachers exhibited a high level of supervisory needs, with a grand mean of 2.99. Diversity of learners had the highest mean (3.02), followed by curriculum planning (3.01) and learning environment (3.00). Content knowledge and pedagogy (2.96) and assessment and reporting (2.95) had slightly lower means but remained within the high-need category.
6. **Predictors of Work Engagement.** Efficacy and job satisfaction were found to be significant positive predictors of work engagement. In contrast, supervisory needs, training, years of teaching experience, and minimum educational attainment were not significant predictors. Among the categories of highest educational attainment, having a Diploma in Early Childhood Education was associated with higher work engagement, while being at the CAR doctoral level was associated with lower work engagement.

Conclusions

Work engagement among kindergarten teachers is significantly influenced by their level of efficacy and job satisfaction. Additionally, holding a Diploma in Early Childhood Education is associated with higher work engagement, while being at the CAR doctoral level is associated with lower engagement. Overall, internal psychological factors, particularly efficacy and job satisfaction, play a more critical role in shaping work engagement than demographic and professional background variables.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. School District Supervisors and School Heads may organize district-based trainings focusing on curriculum planning and strategies for managing diverse learners in alignment with current curriculum demands.
2. Instructional leaders may strengthen mentoring, coaching, and technical assistance, particularly in areas of learner diversity and instructional planning.
3. Schools may implement wellness and motivation programs to sustain teachers' efficacy and work engagement.
4. School administrators may ensure that teachers pursuing graduate studies are provided with manageable workloads to prevent disengagement.
5. Policymakers may consider enhancing compensation packages, including health benefits, to address increasing professional demands.
6. School heads may initiate recognition programs to further improve teachers' job satisfaction.

7. Future researchers may explore additional variables influencing work engagement and incorporate qualitative approaches to better understand teachers' experiences.

Proposed Action Plan Matrix

Title: *Upskilling Supervisory Support in Curriculum Planning and Inclusive Classroom Practices*

Type: District-Based Mid-Year INSET Seminar-Training

Objectives	Activities/Strategies	Persons Involved	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Success Indicators
1. Strengthen teachers' skills in curriculum planning aligned with diverse learners	Conduct workshop on curriculum planning and lesson design (Standards-based and differentiated)	School Heads, Master Teachers, Resource Speakers, Kindergarten Teachers	Day 2–3 (INSET Week)	Laptop, projector, lesson plan templates, curriculum guides	100% of participants produce a curriculum-aligned lesson plan
2. Enhance teachers' competence in managing diverse learners through inclusive practices	Seminar-workshop on Inclusive Education and Differentiated Instruction (case analysis, group tasks)	Resource Speakers, School Heads, Teachers	Day 3	Modules, handouts, case scenarios	At least 90% of participants demonstrate appropriate strategies for diverse learners
3. Improve school heads' supervisory, coaching, and feedback skills	Training on Glickman's Developmental Supervision and Coaching Techniques (role play, simulation)	School Heads, PSDS, Teachers	Day 1 & 4	Presentation materials, supervision tools, rubrics	School heads demonstrate appropriate supervisory approaches during simulation
4. Promote collaborative instructional support between teachers and school heads	Peer coaching and mentoring sessions (Teacher–School Head pairing)	School Heads, Teachers	Day 4	Coaching guides, observation tools	Active participation of 100% of participants in coaching sessions
5. Develop sustainable instructional supervisory plans	Workshop on crafting Teacher Instructional Supervisory Support Plan (TISSP)	School Heads, Teachers	Day 5	Templates, writing materials	100% of participants submit completed action plans
6. Assess learning and effectiveness of the training	Conduct pre-test, post-test, and evaluation of the seminar-training	Facilitators, Participants	Day 1 & Day 5	Test questionnaires, evaluation forms	Significant increase in post-test scores; positive evaluation results
7. Strengthen teacher motivation and engagement	Conduct reflection sessions and recognition/awarding ceremony	School Heads, Organizers	Day 5	Certificates, tokens	Increased teacher satisfaction and engagement based on feedback

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan

Tools: Pre-test and post-test, observation checklist, reflection journals, evaluation forms

Frequency: Daily monitoring and end-of-training evaluation

Responsible: Monitoring and Evaluation Team, School Heads

Expected Output

- Curriculum-aligned lesson plans
- Demonstration teaching outputs
- Teacher Instructional Supervisory Support Plan (TISSP)

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study followed established ethical guidelines. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained after explaining the purpose, procedures, and participants' rights, including withdrawal at any time. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured, with no identifying information collected. All data were securely stored and used only for academic purposes in accordance with the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173). The study posed no risk, and no incentives or compensation were provided.

REFERENCES

- Albrecht, S. L., Green, C. R., & Marty, A. (2021). Meaningful work, job resources, and employee engagement. *Sustainability*, 13(7), 4045.
- Alshmemri, M., Shahwan-Akl, L., & Maude, P. (2017). Herzberg's two-factor theory. *Life Science Journal*, 14(5), 12-16.
- Baggay, C. T., Bautista, B. J. D., Celestino, C. F., Corral, E. G., Delos Santos, A. R., Francisco, K. A. B., & Seciban, D. A. (2021). School heads' instructional supervisions and its impact on teachers' job satisfaction. *Online Submission*, 6(3), 1–16.
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2024). Job demands–resources theory: Frequently asked questions. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 29(3), 188–204.
- Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., & Sanz-Vergel, A. (2023). Job demands–resources theory: Ten years later. *Annual review of organizational psychology and organizational behavior*, 10(1), 25-53.
- Crowhurst, P., & Cornish, L. (2020). Factors in agency development: A supervisory teaching perspective. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 45(9), 24–41.
- Gallego, P., & Caingcoy, M. (2020). Competencies and professional development needs of kindergarten teachers.
- Glickman, C. D. (1992). *Supervision in Transition: 1992 Yearbook of the Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development, 125 N. West Street, Alexandria, VA 22314 (Stock No. 610-92000: \$19.95).
- Han, Y., & Wang, Y. (2021). Investigating the correlation among Chinese EFL teachers' self-efficacy, work engagement, and reflection. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 763234.
- Heng, Q., & Chu, L. (2023). Self-efficacy, reflection, and resilience as predictors of work engagement among English teachers. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1160681.

- Hussain, M. S., Khan, S. A., & Bidar, M. C. (2022). Self-efficacy of teachers: A review of the literature. *Multi-Disciplinary Research Journal*, 10(1), 110–116.
- Maquidato, J. N. C., & Bayani, R. T. (2024). Workload and work engagement among teachers: A descriptive-correlational study. *EPRA International Journal of Environmental Economics, Commerce and Educational Management*, 11(7), 136–148.
- Mufidah, N., Arafat, Y., & Puspita, Y. (2021). The effect of training and teaching experience on teacher performance. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Education Universitas PGRI Palembang (INCoEPP 2021)* (pp. 160–166). Atlantis Press.
- Oyekunle, O. (2024). Influence of motivation and availability of resources on teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Minna, Niger State. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research & Review*, 5(2), 25–58.
- Pranoto, Y. K., Utami, D. R., Latiana, L., & Ahmadi, F. (2021). Do teachers' experiences and ages contribute to their teaching performance? In *Proceedings of the 11th Annual International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management Singapore* (pp. 3515–3522).
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2003). *Utrecht work engagement scale: Preliminary manual*. Occupational Health Psychology Unit, Utrecht University.
- Schunk, D. H., & DiBenedetto, M. K. (2021). Self-efficacy and human motivation. In *Advances in motivation science* (Vol. 8, pp. 153–179). Elsevier.
- Setyaningsih, S., & Sunaryo, W. (2021). Optimizing transformational leadership strengthening, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction to increase teacher commitment. *International Journal of Instruction*, 14(4), 427–438.
- Shu, K. (2022). Teachers' commitment and self-efficacy as predictors of work engagement and well-being. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 850204.
- Tschannen-Moran, M., & Hoy, A. W. (2001). Teacher efficacy: Capturing an elusive construct. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(7), 783–805.
- Wang, P., Chu, P., Wang, J., Pan, R., Sun, Y., Yan, M., & Zhang, D. (2020). Association between job stress and organizational commitment in three types of Chinese university teachers: Mediating effects of job burnout and job satisfaction. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 576768.
- Wisudawati, W. N. (2023). Descriptive study of teacher self-efficacy with gender perspective in kindergarten teachers. *Journal of Southeast Asia Psychology*, 11, 65–77.
- Zang, L., & Feng, Y. (2023). Relationship between job satisfaction and work engagement in Chinese kindergarten teachers: Vocational delay of gratification as a mediator. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1114519.